

A Theory of Strong Electrolytes in Solution Based on a New Statistics. III. Equilibrium Phenomena : Activity Coefficients.

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A theory of strong electrolytes in solution, developed earlier by using a new distribution formula in place of the Boltzmann statistics, has been applied for calculating the activity coefficients of some 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes in aqueous solution. Two different distribution formulae, holding respectively for the cases when (i) $b_{+-} \ll -b_{\pm}$, and (ii) $b_{+-} \sim b_{\pm}$, where the b 's are the appropriate ionic exclusion volumes, have been studied. The Poisson equation has been shown to be solvable for both of two limiting cases, viz. when the potential is low, as also high; and a composite solution has been built up by fitting the two together appropriately. The performance of both the solutions in calculation of activity coefficients has been studied over the entire concentration range. The second order correction for mutual overlap of ionic exclusion volumes at higher concentrations, has been introduced. Finally, two possible relations between the two adjustable parameters entering into the theory, namely the ion-size parameter a and the exclusion parameter b , have both been considered in respect to their effect on the course of the calculated activity coefficient—concentration curves.

The calculated results for some typical a values, have been compared with experimental data for alkali and alkaline earth halides.

The application of distribution formulae different from that of Boltzmann for calculating the ionic charge density ρ in the neighbourhood of any central ion in the solution of a strong electrolyte, as in the theory of Debye and Hückel¹, has been investigated in a number of papers^{2,3,4,5}. Of these, the Dutta-Bagchi⁶ ionic distribution formula, obtained from the simple assumption that there is an effect of mutual physical exclusion between ions due to their finite sizes⁷, is

$$\frac{n_{\pm}}{1 - n_{\mp} b_{+-}} = \frac{1/b_{\pm}}{e^{\pm z_{\pm} e\psi/kT} + 1} \quad (1)$$

1. P. Debye and E. Huckel, *Phys. Z.*, 1923, 24, 185, 305.
2. H. Falkenhagen, in "Modern Aspects of Electrochemistry", II, ed. J. O'M. Bockris, Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1959, p. 1.
3. (a) S. N. Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 27, 199, 204.
(b) S. N. Bagchi, *Naturwiss.*, 1952, 39, 299; M. Dutta, *ibid.* 1952, 39, 569; 1953, 40, 51.
4. M. Eigen, and E. Wicke, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 702; (references to earlier papers given.)
5. H. Falkenhagen, M. Leist and G. Kelbg, *Ann. d. Phys.*, 1952, (6) 11, 51.
H. Falkenhagen, and G. Kelbg, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1952, 56, 834. (see also H. Falkenhagen and G. Kelbg, *Z. phys. Chem.*, 1953, 202, 56, for reversion to the Boltzmann formula).
H. Falkenhagen, and G. Kelbg, *Ann. d. Phys.*, 1952, (6), 11, 60; 1954, 14, 391.
M. Dutta, *Ann. d. Phys.*, 1954, (6), 14, 188.
6. M. Dutta and S. N. Bagchi, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1950, 24, 61.
7. M. Dutta, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1947, 13, 247; 1948 14, 163; 1951, 27, 445.

where n_{\pm} are the number-densities of positive *or* negative ions (valency z_{+} , z_{-}) at a point where the mean electric potential is ψ ; b_{\pm} and b_{+-} are respectively the exclusion volumes for mutual close approach between two like ions (b_{+} and b_{-}) and two unlike ions (b_{+-}); and ν_{\pm} are distribution parameters. If it be assumed that the mutual exclusion between like ions is much more significant than that between unlike ions (i.e. $b_{+-} \ll b_{\pm}$), then equation (1) reduces to

$$n_{\pm} = \frac{1/b_{\pm}}{\nu_{\pm} \pm z_{\pm} e\psi/kT + 1} \quad (2)$$

which is similar in *appearance* to the distribution formula of Bagchi^{8a}, though there are important differences also.*

The above rigorously deduced distribution formula (2) with the original simple interpretation of the various parameters involved has been applied by Dutta and Sengupta⁹, and Sengupta¹⁰ for the calculation of mean ionic activity coefficients of some 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes at different concentrations, following in general the method of Bagchi with some important modifications. The present paper is in essence an extension and amplification of this earlier work. Opportunity has been taken during the present calculations to discuss critically certain distinctive features of our method, namely,

(i) the composite method of solution of the Poisson equation (for this, only the low potential solution, as also the low and high potential solutions compositely together, have been used for calculation of activity coefficients over the entire concentration range);

(ii) the overlap correction for ionic exclusion volumes¹¹. both for mutual close approach among like ions only, as also for that among unlike ions also (for this, calculation of activity coefficients over the entire concentration range has been carried out both with and without the aforesaid overlap corrections);

(iii) the nature of the approximation $b_{+-} \ll b_{\pm}$ (for this, the distribution formula (1) which does not involve this approximation, is also used, along with formula (2) for calculation of activity coefficients);

(iv) the nature of the relation, if any, between the two arbitrary parameters entering into the theory, namely, the ion-size parameter a and the ionic exclusion parameter b (for this, both of two possible relations between b and a have been used in the calculation of activity coefficients, in some typical cases).

* Regarding the unhappy controversy in respect of identity, method of derivation, etc. of the various different distribution formulae proposed, see the appropriate review articles^{9,8}.

8. O. Redlich, in "Annual Reviews of Physical Chemistry", VI, ed. G. K. Rollefson and R. E. Powell, Annual Reviews Inc., Stanford, 1955.

9. M. Dutta and M. Sengupta, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1954, 20, 1.

10. M. Sengupta, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1956, 22, 13.

11. M. Dutta, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1952, 18, 81.

Calculations using the distribution formula (2). The detailed calculations having already been reported earlier^{9,10}, we recapitulate only the important steps for the sake of easy reference. The expression for ρ at any point where the potential is ψ , obtained by using the formula (2), leads to two distinct expressions according as ψ is large or small, viz

$$\rho_{\psi \sim \infty} = -\frac{z_- e}{b_-} \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_{\psi \sim 0} = -\frac{e^2}{kT} \left[\sum n_i^0 z_i^2 - \sum n_i^0 z_i^2 b_i \right] \psi \quad (4)$$

the n_i^0 's being the stoichiometric number densities of i th ions in solution. The maximum charge density of negative ions clustering close round a central positive ion (where ψ is maximal) is thus seen to approach the physically limiting value $-\frac{z_- e}{b_-}$, and does not become infinite as in the Debye-Hückel theory. Also, the Poisson equation is seen to assume two distinct limiting forms according as ψ is large or small, so that in addition to the usual Debye-Hückel solution, a solution can also be worked out for the case when ψ is large. In addition to its interest in electrolyte solution theory itself (e.g. for polyvalent ions in solution), this result promises to be significant for the interpretation of various other types of charge interactions in solution which are amenable to treatment by the Debye-Hückel method and where the potentials involved are known to be high, e.g. macro-ions in solution, colloidal particles in suspensions, etc.¹²

The Poisson equation in dimensionless variables then becomes, with spherical symmetry,

$$\frac{1}{\xi^2} \frac{d}{d\xi} \xi^2 \frac{d\lambda}{d\xi} = \lambda \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{\xi^2} \frac{d}{d\xi} \xi^2 \frac{d\lambda}{d\xi} = m_+ \quad (6)$$

where

$$\lambda = e\psi/kT, \quad \xi = \kappa r \quad (7)$$

$$\kappa^2 = \frac{4\pi e^2}{\epsilon kT} \left[\sum n_i^0 z_i^2 - \sum n_i^0 z_i^2 b_i \right]^* \quad (8)$$

$$m_{\pm} = \pm \frac{z_{\mp}}{b_{\mp}^0} \frac{1}{\sum n_i^0 z_i^2 - \sum n_i^0 z_i^2 b_i} \quad (9)$$

with the solutions :

$$\lambda_1 = A \frac{e^{\xi}}{\xi} + B \frac{e^{-\xi}}{\xi} \quad (10)$$

$$\lambda_2 = m_+ \left[\frac{\xi^2}{6} + C + \frac{H}{\xi} \right] \quad (11)$$

* Henceforth in this section, we write b^0 in place of b so as to specialise the formulae for the case being considered, i.e. neglect of overlap correction of exclusion volumes.

12. E. J. W. Verwey and J. Th. G. Overbeek, "Theory of the Stability of Lyophobic Colloids", Elsevier Pub. Co., Amsterdam, 1948.

The boundary conditions for the determination of the constants are the usual ones :

$$r \rightarrow \infty, \psi \rightarrow 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\int_a^\infty \frac{d\psi}{dr} dS = -\frac{4\pi}{\epsilon} z_+ e \quad (13)$$

a being the maximum distance from the central ion, within which no other charge can penetrate.

Both these conditions can be applied straightaway to the expression for λ_1 , giving (save for the small difference in the expressions for κ) the well-known Debye-Hückel result :

$$(\lambda_{\pm})_1 = \frac{z_{\pm} e^2 \kappa e^{\xi_{a_{\pm}}}}{\epsilon kT(1 + \xi_{a_{\pm}})} \frac{e^{-\xi}}{\xi} \quad (14)$$

The expression for λ_2 shows that it passes through a minimum at $\xi = (3H)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, so that the first condition is inapplicable. The other condition is applicable nevertheless, giving

$$H_{\pm} = \frac{z_{\pm} e^2 \kappa}{m_{\pm} \epsilon kT} + \frac{\kappa^2 a_{\pm}^2}{3} = \frac{z_{\pm} \kappa^2 b_{\mp}^2}{z_{\mp} 4\pi} + \frac{(\kappa a_{\pm})^2}{3} = \frac{g_{\pm}}{3}, \text{ say.} \quad (15)$$

Since however it is this expression for the potential which is of greater interest to us, therefore, in order to be able to utilise it notwithstanding the above difficulty, use is made of the 'method of fit' devised by Bagchi^{2a}. In this method, λ_2 is used in conjunction with λ_1 , after fitting them suitably together by the conditions*

$$(\lambda_1)_{\xi_1} = m_+ = (\lambda_2)_{\xi_1} \quad (16)$$

$$\left(\frac{d\lambda_1}{d\xi} \right)_{\xi_1} = \left(\frac{d\lambda_2}{d\xi} \right)_{\xi_1} \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) in conjunction with the first of equations (16) gives

$$\xi_1 = (1 + g)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \quad (18)$$

whereafter the second of equations (16) gives

$$C = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - (1 + g)^{\frac{3}{2}} \right] \quad (19)$$

so that λ_2 becomes :

$$(\lambda_{\pm})_2 = m_{\pm} \left[\frac{\xi^2}{6} + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ 1 - (1 + g_{\pm})^{\frac{3}{2}} \right\} + \frac{H_{\pm}}{\xi} \right] \quad (20)$$

The first of equations (16) gives an expression for B :

$$B = m_+ \left[(1 + g_+)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \right] e^{\left[(1 + g_+)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \right]} \quad (21)$$

however, this will be shown to be of little consequence.

* The fit at $\lambda = m$ ensures that the second derivatives of λ are also equal at the point of fit, for the rest, it is arbitrary.

The nature of the functional dependence of the potential on distance from the central ion, and the significance of the 'method of fit' employed for the subsequent calculations, may be grasped better from a graphical representation. In fig. 1 is shown the plot of $a\lambda$ against ξ for some different values of ξ_a , for a central positive ion in the solution of a 1-1 electrolyte, with b° given, for example, by $b^\circ = \frac{4}{3}\pi a^3$. At $\xi_a=5$, for instance, the potential from the ion-surface onwards is first given by $\lambda_2(\xi)$. At the point $\xi=\xi_1$ ($=5.308$, in this case, from equation 18), the transition from λ_2 to λ_1 takes place, and the potential is given thereafter by $\lambda_1(\xi)$ (with equation 21). The Debye-Hückel potential function (equation 14, which we refer to so, notwithstanding the small difference in κ) for the same value of ξ_a is also shown alongside (dotted curve), though it does not have any significance yet. As ξ_a is

Fig. 1. Fall of potential from the ion surface onwards, for three different values of $\xi_a = \kappa a$ — Debye-Hückel solution (equation 14); — Low potential solution (equations 10, 21, with $A=0$); — High potential solution (equations 20, 15).

decreased, the point of fit approaches closer to the ion-surface ($\xi_1 \rightarrow \xi_a$) with the result that the stretch $\lambda_2(\xi)$ is progressively shortened; also the Debye-Hückel curve runs closer and closer alongside. When $\xi_a = \xi_1$ (this happens at $\xi_a = 3.79$, from equation 18), the point of fit being now on the ion-surface itself, the entire potential curve is given by $\lambda_1(\xi)$, which is also now indistinguishable from the Debye-Hückel curve by virtue of equations (13,16,17), the two coalescing together all-along. (For still smaller values of ξ_a (at $\xi_a = 2$, for instance) the $\lambda_1(\xi)$ curve separates once again from the Debye-Hückel curve).

The value of the potential at the ion-surface itself is by far the most important¹³. It is seen from the figure that this continues to be given by $\lambda_2(\xi_a)$ so long as $\xi_a < \xi_1$, (i.e. at higher concentrations). At $\xi_a = \xi_1$ ($= 3.79$), the surface potential is given indifferently by $\lambda_1(\xi_a)$ or D. H. (ξ_a); but for smaller values of ξ_a still, it would rather more appropriately be taken to be given by D. H. (ξ_a), because of

13. M. Sengupta, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1953, 27, 627.

the well-known success of the Debye-Hückel results at lower concentrations. That this is permissible is seen at once from the conditions of fit, which ensure that the $\lambda_2(\xi_a)$ and D. H. (ξ_a) curves touch together (via $\lambda_1(\xi_a)$) at the critical point ($\xi_a = \xi_1$), with identical slopes.

The calculation of the electrical free energy of the solution, and thereafter of the mean ionic activity coefficient f_{\pm} follows next by the usual Debye-Hückel procedure. For the former, one obtains, after changing (for convenience in the subsequent differentiation) the integration over e to that over κ by the relation $ed\kappa = \kappa de$ (c. f. equation 8), the following expressions :

- (a) When the surface-potential of both positive and negative ions is given by λ_1 ,

$$W = -\frac{kT}{4\pi} \int_0^{\kappa} \frac{\kappa^2 \sum n_i^0 z_i^2 / (1 + \kappa a_i)}{\sum n_i z_i - \sum n_i z_i b_i} d\kappa \tag{22}$$

- (b) When the surface-potential of both positive and negative ions is given by λ_2 ,

$$W = \frac{kT}{2} \left[\frac{z_+ a_+^2}{b_+^0} \int_0^{\kappa} \frac{\kappa}{\sum z_+ - \sum n_+^0 z_+ b_+^0} \left[1 - \frac{1}{(\kappa a_+)^2} \left\{ 1 - (1 + g_+)^{\frac{2}{3}} \right\} \right] d\kappa \right] \tag{23}$$

- (c) When the surface-potential of the positive ion, say, is given by λ_1 and that of the negative ion by λ_2 (a situation which arises for unequal size or unequal charge of the ions)*

$$W = -n_+^0 z_+^2 \int_0^e \frac{z_+ e}{\epsilon} \frac{\kappa}{1 + \kappa a_+} de + \frac{n_-^0 z_- kT m_-}{2e} \int_0^e \left[(\kappa a_-)^2 + \left\{ 1 - (1 + g_-)^{\frac{2}{3}} \right\} \right] de \tag{24}$$

The expressions for f_{\pm} , given by :

$$\ln f_{\pm} = \frac{\gamma_+ \ln f_+ + \gamma_- \ln f_-}{\gamma_+ + \gamma_-} = \frac{1}{\gamma_+ + \gamma_-} \frac{1}{kT} \sum \gamma_i \frac{\partial W}{\partial n_i} \tag{25}$$

(ν_+ , ν_- being the numbers of positive and negative ions produced from one molecule of the electrolyte ; $\nu_+ + \nu_- = \nu$), obtained for the above three cases are respectively :

- (a) $\ln f_{\pm} = -\frac{z_+ z_-}{\sum z_i} \frac{e^2 \kappa}{\epsilon kT} \left\{ \frac{S}{2} \sum \frac{z_i}{1 + \kappa a_i} + (1 - S) \sum z_i \theta_i \right\}$ (26)

where $S = \frac{\sum n_i z_i^2 - 2 \sum n_i z_i b_i^0}{\sum n_i z_i - \sum n_i z_i b_i^0}$ (27)

$$\theta_i = \frac{1}{(\kappa a_i)^2} \left\{ \ln(1 + \kappa a_i) - \kappa a_i + \frac{1}{2} (\kappa a_i)^2 \right\} \tag{28}$$

* The reverse case (less frequently encountered in the numerical calculations, below) when the surface potential of the positive ion is given by λ_2 and that of the negative ion by λ_1 leads to expressions analogous to equations (32, 38 and 46)

$$(b) \quad \ln f_{\pm} = \frac{z_+ z_-}{\sum z_i} \sum \frac{m_+}{2} \left[\frac{(\kappa a_+)^2}{2} + (P + \phi_+)(1 - S) - \frac{S}{2} \left\{ (1 + g_+)^{\frac{2}{3}} - 1 \right\} \right] \quad (29)$$

where
$$P = \frac{1}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{1}{3}} \tan^{-1} \sqrt{3} - \frac{1}{2} \ln 3 \equiv 0.5551 \quad (30)$$

$$\phi_i(g_i) = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left[(1 + g_i)^{\frac{2}{3}} + (1 + g_i)^{\frac{1}{3}} + 1 \right] - \frac{1}{2} (1 + g_i)^{\frac{2}{3}} - \sqrt{\frac{1}{3}} \tan^{-1} \frac{2(1 + g_i)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\sqrt{3}} + 1 \quad (31)$$

$$(c) \quad \ln f_{\pm} = \frac{z_+ z_-}{\sum z_i} \left[-\frac{z_+ e^2 \kappa}{\epsilon k T} \left\{ \frac{S}{2} \frac{1}{(1 + \kappa a_+)} + \theta_+(1 - S) \right\} - \frac{m_-}{2} \left\{ \frac{(\kappa a_-)^2}{2} + (P + \phi_-)(1 - S) - \frac{S}{2} \left\{ (1 + g_-)^{\frac{2}{3}} - 1 \right\} \right\} \right] \quad (32)$$

*The overlap correction for ionic exclusion volumes**—The quantities b are, as mentioned, the volumes in exclusive command of the individual ions. For rigid spherical particles of a very dilute assembly where close approach between the particles is very infrequent, the ionic exclusion volumes are given by: $b^{\circ} = \frac{4\pi}{3}$ (diameter)³. With increase in concentration, the frequency of close encounter between the particles increases; the average volume of physical space over which any ion can still be considered to have exclusive command, decreases as a result from the above limiting value. The expression for the average exclusion volume of each particle in a system of n° similar particles per c.c. after introducing second order overlap correction, has been shown by Dutta¹¹ to be given by :

$$b = b^{\circ} \left(1 - \frac{17}{96} n^{\circ} b^{\circ} \right) \quad (33)$$

the value of the numerical coefficient differing slightly from that given by Boltzmann¹⁵. Since close approach among like ions only is taken the consideration in deducing the distribution formula (2), therefore the appropriate form of equation (33) to be used in this case is ;

$$b_{\pm} = b_{\pm}^{\circ} \left(1 - \frac{17}{96} n_{\pm}^{\circ} b_{\pm}^{\circ} \right) \quad (34)$$

Due to this dependence of b_{\pm} on the concentrations n_{\pm}° the scheme of calculations is modified only when differentiation with respect to n_{\pm}° is encountered, as in the derivation of equations (26, 29, 32). One then obtains instead, respectively :

$$(a) \quad \ln f_{\pm} = -\frac{z_+ z_-}{\sum z_i} \frac{e^2 \kappa}{\epsilon k T} \left\{ \frac{S'}{2} \sum \frac{z_i}{1 + \kappa a_i} + (1 - S) \sum z_i \theta_i \right\} \quad (35)$$

where
$$S' = \frac{\sum n_i^{\circ} z_i^3 - 2 \sum n_i^{\circ 2} z_i^2 b_i + \frac{17}{96} \sum n_i^{\circ 3} z_i^3 b_i^{\circ 3}}{\sum n_i^{\circ} z_i^3 - \sum n_i^{\circ 2} z_i^2 b_i} \quad (36)$$

* The concentration dependence of the quantities b has also been pointed out (though not used in the calculations) by Falkenhagen and Kelbg¹⁴ in their derivation of the distribution formula by the Born Green method.

14. M. Falkenhagen and G. Kelbg, *Naturwiss.*, 1955, 1, 10; *Z. phys. Chem.*, 1955, 204, 111.

15. L. Boltzmann, 'Vorlesungen über Gastheorie', 1923, p. 165. (also, ref. 21a, p. 289).

$$(b) \quad \ln f_{\pm} = \frac{z_+ z_-}{\sum z_i} \sum \frac{m_+}{2} \left[\frac{(\kappa a_+)^2}{2} \frac{b_+^0}{b_-} + (P + \phi'_+) \left(\frac{b_+^0}{b_-} - S' \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (1 + g'_+)^{2/3} - 1 \right\} \right. \\ \left. \left\{ S' - \frac{z_+ \kappa^3}{z_- 2\pi g_+} (b_-^0 - b_-) \right\} \right] \quad (37)$$

$$(c) \quad \ln f_{\pm} = \frac{z_+ z_-}{\sum z_i} \left[-\frac{z_+ e^2 \kappa \{ S' \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{(1 + \kappa a_+)} - \theta_+(1 - S') \}}{\epsilon k T} - \frac{m_- \{ \frac{(\kappa a_-)^2 b_+^0}{2} + (P + \phi'_-) \left(\frac{b_+^0}{b_+} - S' \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (1 + g'_-)^{2/3} - 1 \right\} \right\} \left\{ S' - \frac{z_- \kappa^3}{z_+ 2\pi g_-} (b_+^0 - b_+) \right\} \right] \quad (38)$$

Here,

$$\kappa^3 = \frac{4\pi e^2}{\epsilon k T} \left[\sum n_i z_i^2 - \sum n_i^+ z_i^+ z_i^- \right] \quad (39)$$

$$m_{\pm} = \frac{z_{\mp}}{b_{\mp}} \frac{1}{\sum n_i z_i - \sum n_i^+ z_i^+ z_i^-} \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{g'_{\pm}}{3} = \frac{z_{\pm} \kappa^3 b_{\mp}}{z_{\mp} 4\pi} + \frac{(\kappa a_{\pm})^3}{3} \quad (41)$$

Calculations using the distribution formula (1)*

In the distribution formula (1) the mutual exclusion between oppositely charged ions is also taken into consideration in addition to that between similarly charged ions (i.e. it is assumed that $b_{+-} \sim b_{\pm}$). In using this formula for the calculation of ρ it is however necessary to assume from the outset that the quantities b_{\pm} are mutually equal, and further, identical with b_{+-} .** One then obtains similarly as before,

$$\rho \psi \sim \infty = -\frac{z_- e}{b^0} \quad (42)$$

$$\rho \psi \sim 0 = -\frac{e^2 \psi}{k T} \sum n_i^+ z_i^+ \quad (43)$$

Proceeding exactly as before one obtains finally for the three different cases considered,

$$(a) \quad \ln f_{\pm} = -\frac{z_+ z_- e^2}{2\epsilon k T} \frac{\kappa}{1 + \kappa a} \quad (44)$$

$$(b) \quad \ln f_{\pm} = \frac{z_+ z_-}{\sum z_i} \sum \frac{m_+}{2} \left[\frac{(\kappa a)^2}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (1 + g_+)^{2/3} - 1 \right\} \right] \quad (45)$$

$$(c) \quad \ln f_{\pm} = \frac{z_+ z_-}{\sum z_i} \left[-\frac{z_+ e^2}{2\epsilon k T} \frac{\kappa}{1 + \kappa a} - \sum \frac{m_-}{2} \left\{ \frac{(\kappa a)^2}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (1 - g_-)^{2/3} - 1 \right\} \right\} \right] \quad (46)$$

Here,

$$\kappa^3 = \frac{4\pi e^2}{\epsilon k T} \sum n_i z_i^2 \quad (47)$$

$$m_{\pm} = \frac{z_{\mp}}{b^0} \frac{1}{\sum n_i^+ z_i^+} \quad (48)$$

$$\frac{g_{\pm}}{3} = \frac{z_{\pm}}{z_{\mp}} \frac{\kappa^3 b^0}{4\pi} + \frac{(\kappa a)^3}{3} \quad (49)$$

* A different version of this, with a correction for the proper volume of solvent molecules^{ab} has been applied by Bagchi^{ab} and (correctly) by Dejak¹⁶ for calculation of activity coefficients by the Gronwall method.

** Because of the correlation between the quantities b and a (discussed below), this requires also that $a_+ = a_- = a$, say.

16. C. Dejak in "An International Electrolytes Symposium", ed. B. Pesce, Pergamon Press, London, 1962, p. 266, 281.

The above result (47) shows, as has already been pointed out by Falkenhagen and Schmutzer¹⁷ for the case of the Eigen-Wicke distribution formula, that the consideration of equal mutual exclusion by all ions, irrespective of the sign of their charge, gives an expression for the thickness of the ion-atmosphere $1/\kappa$, which is identical with that in the Debye-Hückel theory (and is therefore free from the exclusion parameter b). The equation (44) being thus exactly the same as the well-known Debye-Hückel expression for $\ln f_{\pm}$ with ion-size correction, Falkenhagen and Schmutzer¹⁷ have sought to introduce into it the effect of mutual ionic exclusion by incorporation of an additional covolume (i.e., b) dependent term in a manner indicated already by Rysselberghe and Eisenberg¹⁸.

The above formulae can be modified as before for the *overlap correction* of exclusion volumes. Since in the distribution formula (1) the mutual exclusion between all ions (irrespective of sign of charge) is taken into consideration, therefore the appropriate form of the expression (33) to be used here is

$$b = b^{\circ} \left[1 - \frac{17}{96} (n_{+}^{\circ} + n_{-}^{\circ}) b^{\circ} \right] \quad (50)$$

The expression (45) obtained from the high potential solution is then modified, and one obtains :

$$\ln f_{\pm} = \frac{z_{+} z_{-}}{\sum z_i} \sum \frac{m_{+}}{2} \left[\frac{(\kappa a)^3}{2} \left(\frac{b^{\circ}}{b} \right) + (P + \phi'_{+}) \left(\frac{b^{\circ}}{b} - 1 \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (1 + g'_{+})^{\frac{3}{2}} - 1 \right\} \left\{ 1 - \frac{z_{+} \kappa^3}{z_{-} 2\pi g_{+}} (b^{\circ} - b) \right\} \right] \quad (51)$$

where the quantities m_{\pm} and g'_{\pm} are given by the equations (48) and (49), with b in place of b° .

The relation between the quantities a and b . The different expressions for activity coefficient deduced above are generally two-parameter in nature, involving the two unknown quantities a and b . Of these, the ion-size parameter a (c.f. the boundary condition equation 13) represents the radius of the largest sphere surrounding any ion within which no other charge can penetrate. It therefore represents either the ionic diameter (assumption : charge located at the centre of the ionic spheres), or the ionic radius (charge resides on the ion surface). We have hitherto used this latter interpretation of a . The exclusion parameters b_{+-} , b_{\pm} enter into the statistical theory of assemblies of *charged* particles⁷ while considering the distribution of the ions in different potential energy layers in physical space, under the restriction that each elementary cell into which the physical space is supposed to be subdivided can at most accommodate only one particle at a time. Though these exclusion cell volumes b_{+-} , b_{\pm} may conceivably be Coulomb-interaction dependent to some extent (this would justify somewhat the approximation $b_{+-} \ll b_{\pm}$ used in the derivation

17. H. Falkenhagen and E. Schmutzer, *Naturwiss.*, 1953, **40**, 314, 602.

18. P. Van Rysselberghe and S. Eisenberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 3030 ; 1940, **62**, 451.

of the distribution formula 2), still their predominant characteristic as the mutual exclusion parameters of *uncharged* rigid spheres remains. (For highly solvated ions, this rigid-sphere exclusion could even possibly outweigh the weakened Coulomb interaction, so that then the assumption $b_{+-} \sim b_{\pm}$ would be more plausible). Therefore even for assemblies of charged particles, the quantities b_{+-} , b_{\pm} can to a good first approximation, be taken to be given by $b^{\circ} = \frac{4\pi}{3}(\text{diameter})^3$, and their concentration dependence taken to be more or less of the form assumed already (equation 33).

With our interpretation of a , this would mean therefore that $b_{\mp}^{\circ} = \frac{4\pi}{3}(2a_{\pm})^3$.

We have used this relation presently, as done earlier. However, with the alternate possible interpretation of a as discussed above, the relation between b and a would become: $b_{\pm}^{\circ} = \frac{4\pi}{3}a_{\pm}^3$. The use of this relation (e.g. by Eigen and Wicke⁴; c.f. however, ref. 20, p.64) has also been considered here, in some typical cases.

CALCULATIONS AND RESULTS

The results of numerical calculation of the values of mean activity coefficients of 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes in aqueous solution at 25° ($\epsilon=78.6$) by the use of the different equations deduced above are shown in the following tables 1-5.

Tables 1 and 2 give the results for 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes respectively, for a number of arbitrary a_{+} values, using the distribution formula (2). The ion-size parameter for the negative ion has conveniently been taken generally (except for $a_{+}=2.5 \text{ \AA}$ (1-1) and $a_{+}=3.0 \text{ \AA}$ (2-1), when $a_{+}=a_{-}$) to be the same as the crystallographic radius for the Cl^{-} ion (1.81 \AA), as the halide anions are generally known to be much less hydrated than the cations. The results from both solutions of the Poisson equation, i.e. equation (26) alone (upper figures), as also equations (26) and (32 mostly, or 29) compositely together (lower figures) are given*. The transition concentration** where the low potential solution passes over into the high potential solution, for either (| , |) or both ions (||) of the electrolyte (earlier for the smaller

* For calculations with the equations derived from the high potential solution, the values of the functions $\phi(g)$ and $\frac{1}{3}[(1+g)^{\frac{3}{2}}-1]$ for different values of g were obtained from a graphical plot of these functions on a suitably large scale

** For determining this, the values of λ on the surface of both positive and negative ions, as also of the quantities m_{\pm} , must first be calculated at each concentration, by means of equation (14) or (20, with 15), and (9) respectively. Then, for calculation of f_{\pm} , equation (26), (29) or (32) is to be used according as (i) $\lambda(a_{\pm}) < m_{\pm}$, (ii) $\lambda(a_{\pm}) > m_{\pm}$, or (iii) $\lambda(a_{+}) < m_{+}$ and $\lambda(a_{-}) > m_{-}$, respectively. In keeping with the scheme of the present calculations, equation (26) has nevertheless been used in each case over the entire concentration range, while equations (32) or (29) only above the transition concentration. When overlap correction is considered, the corresponding equations used are (35) over the entire range, and (38) or (37) only above the transition concentration, as determined from the appropriate equations for this case (e. g. equation 40, etc.)

TABLE I

-log f_± for 1-1 electrolytes (distribution formula 2). a₋=1.81 Å

0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	5.0
<i>a₊=1.81 Å</i>											
0.1344	0.2434		0.2955		0.3338		0.3346		0.3091	0.2520	
			0.2963		0.3378		0.3463		0.2852	0.2085	
									0.3362	0.3102	
									0.3079	0.2702	
<i>a₊=2.0 Å</i>											
0.1330	0.2389		0.2857		0.3150		0.3075	0.3029	0.2843		
					0.3104				0.2747		
			0.2871		0.3211			0.3209	0.3127		
					0.3128			0.3086	0.2978		
<i>a₊=2.35 Å</i>											
			0.2671		0.2737			0.2193		0.0548	
			0.2661		0.2688			0.2134		0.0366	
0.1307	0.1955	0.2306	0.2495		0.2871			0.2664		0.2141	
					0.2817			0.2591		0.2027	
					0.2658	0.2804					
<i>a₊=a₋=2.50 Å</i>											
0.1249	0.2049		0.2216		0.1446	0.0089					
	0.2057		0.2273		0.1961	0.1477					
<i>a₊=2.66 Å</i>											
	0.2108		0.2476		0.2221			0.0611			
			0.2437		0.2177			0.0562			
0.1284	0.2196		0.2516	0.2593	0.2522			0.1838			
			0.2463	0.2516	0.2435			0.1747			

TABLE 2

-log f_± for 2-1 electrolytes (distribution formula 2). a₋=1.81 Å

0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.7	0.8	1.0	1.25	1.5	2.0
<i>a₊=2.66 Å</i>										
0.3832				0.5827			0.6133		0.5550	0.3836
				0.5748			0.5879		0.5182	0.3187
0.3833	0.5267			0.5857	0.6146		0.6297		0.6108	0.5378
				0.5821	0.6095		0.6049		0.5754	0.4853
<i>a₊=a₋=3.0 Å</i>										
0.3459		0.4362		0.4402	0.3950		0.1825			
		0.4224		0.4217	0.3819		0.1882			
		0.4408		0.4573	0.4409		0.3673	0.2432	0.0088	
		0.4280		0.4400	0.4260		0.3608	0.2355		
<i>a₊=4.0 Å</i>										
	0.3902	0.4070		0.3761	0.2479	0.1110				
	0.3859	0.3986		0.3688	0.2501	0.1154				
0.3362	0.3936	0.4163	0.4212	0.4171	0.3761		0.2382			
0.3355	0.3899	0.4129	0.4124	0.4061	0.3696		0.2387			

TABLE 3

 $-\log f_{\pm}$ for 1-1 electrolytes (distribution formula 1) $a_{+}=a_{-}$

0.1	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
			<u>$a=1.81 \text{ \AA}$</u>			
0.1355	0.2534	0.3192	0.3910	0.4343	0.4650	0.4885
			0.3909	0.4289	0.4506	0.4648
				0.4258	0.4527	0.4704
			<u>$a=3.0 \text{ \AA}$</u>			
		0.2562	0.303	0.326	0.343	
		0.2542	0.2836	0.2949	0.3010	
			<u>$a=4.0 \text{ \AA}$</u>			
	0.1856	0.221	0.254	0.269	0.281	
		0.2093	0.2237	0.2293	0.2323	

TABLE 4

 $-\log f_{\pm}$ for 2-1 electrolytes (distribution formula 1) $a_{+}=a_{-}$

0.05	0.1	0.5	1.0	1.5
			<u>$a=4.3 \text{ \AA}$</u>	
0.2543	0.3138	0.4560	0.4972	0.5395
0.2542	0.3066	0.3894	0.4029	0.4129
			<u>$a=6.2 \text{ \AA}$</u>	
0.2203	0.2634	0.3566	0.3889	0.4053
0.2146	0.2438	0.2824	0.2886	0.2908

TABLE 5

 $-\log f_{\pm}$ for 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes (distribution formula 2) $a_{+}=a_{-}$ with $b^{\circ} = \frac{4\pi}{3} a^3$

0.1	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	3.0	4.0
			<u>$a=4.5 \text{ \AA} (1-1)$</u>			
0.1082	0.1656	0.1822		0.1736	0.1117	-0.1476
		0.1839		0.1840	0.1582	0.0916
			<u>$a=4.2 \text{ \AA} (2-1)$</u>			
	0.4395	+ 0.4689	0.4645	0.4365	0.2422	
			0.4444	0.4053	0.1192	
	0.4405	+ 0.4735	0.4775	0.4669	0.4058	
			0.454	0.4299	0.3426	

ion in symmetrical electrolytes), is indicated in each case by a vertical line. The lower pair of underlined figures give in each case the corresponding results when overlap correction is taken into account, i.e. equation (35) alone (upper figures), and equations (35) and (38 mostly, or 37) compositely together (lower figures).

Tables 3 and 4 give similarly the results for 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes respectively for a number of a values using the distribution formula (1), i.e. from equation (44) alone, as also compositely with equation (45) for 1-1, or (46 mostly, or 45) for 2-1 electrolytes (upper pair of figures, respectively); and from equations (44) and (51) compositely, taking overlap correction into account (lower underlined figures) for

$a=1.81 \text{ \AA}$ only. As already mentioned, in this case the ion-size parameter must be taken to be the same for both ions; also, the overlap correction applies here only to the high potential solution. The transition concentration* (same here for both ions of symmetrical electrolytes) is indicated as above in each case.

Finally, Table 5 gives the results for one 1-1 and one 2-1 electrolyte from the distribution formula (2), using the second possible relation between the quantities b and a . Here, a_+ has been put equal to a_- ; and, for the 1-1 electrolyte (as in the corresponding case of $a_+ = a_- = 2.50 \text{ \AA}$, in Table 1) only the results from the low potential solution are given.

The results, suitably grouped together, are shown graphically in figures 2-5; those from the distribution formula (2) being shown in figures 2-4, and from formula (1) in fig. 5. In each case, the close running pair of *continuous* curves show the results *without* overlap correction (upper curve: high potential solution, lower curve: low potential solution); the close running pair of *dotted* curves show likewise the results *with* overlap correction (upper dotted - high potential solution with overlap correction, lower dotted - low potential solution with overlap correction). Fig. 2 shows

Fig. 2. $\log f_{\pm}$ vs. concentration for 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes, calculated from distribution formula (2). —without overlap correction (upper curve: high potential solution, equations 29, 32; lower: low potential solution, equation 26). —with overlap correction (upper: high potential solution, equations 37, 38; lower: low potential solution, equation 35).

Fig. 3. Same as in Fig. 2. Lower set of (three) curves for 1-1 electrolyte ($a=1.81 \text{ \AA}$) shows results calculated from formula (1); —without overlap correction (upper; high potential solution, equation 45; lower: low potential solution, equation 44); —with overlap correction (high potential solution, 51).

the results for two different values of the ion-size parameter a_+ for each of 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes. Fig. 3 shows a comparison of the results from the two distribution formulae, for one particular value of the ion-size parameter ($a_+ = a_- = 1.81 \text{ \AA}$), besides showing the results from formula (2) for one more of each of 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes. Fig. 4 shows a comparison of the results obtained from the two different

* Calculated from the appropriate equations for this case, e. g. equation (48), etc. Here also, the activity coefficient equation for the case $\lambda(a_{\pm}) < m_{\pm}$ i. e. equation (44) is used over the whole concentration range, while equation (46) or (45) only above the transition concentration.

interpretations of the relation between the parameters b and a (results shown for one 1-1 and one 2-1 electrolyte in case of each relation, of suitably different a values ; for the 1-1 electrolytes, only the results from the low potential solution given). Fig. 5 shows finally the results from the distribution formula (1) for two different values of the ion-size parameter for each of 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes, without overlap correction in every case.

Fig. 4. Same as in Fig. 2. for two different interpretations of the relation between a and b . namely (a) $b_{\pm}^0 = \frac{4\pi}{3} (2a_{\pm})^3$ and (b) $b_{\pm}^0 = \frac{4\pi}{3} a_{\pm}^3$.

Fig. 5. $\log f_{\pm}$ for 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes from distribution formula (1), without overlap correction. In each case, lower curve : low potential (Debye-Huckel) solution (equation 44); upper : high potential solution (equation 45).

For the sake of comparison of the calculated results with experimental data, the observed values of mean ionic activity coefficient of some typical alkali and alkaline earth halides and nitrates are also shown. The experimental values have been obtained from the compilation of Harned and Owen^{19a}. The tabulated γ_{\pm} values at the different molalities m were converted to $\log f_{\pm}$ by the relation : $\ln f_{\pm} = \ln \gamma_{\pm} (1 + 0.01802 \nu m)$, and the molalities into molarities by the appropriate empirical relation for each electrolyte^{19b} (accuracy $\pm 0.05\%$).

The results of calculations given above show :

1. The familiar initial decrease of f_{\pm} values (from unity at infinite dilution) with increasing concentration, followed by a gradual re-increase at higher concentrations ; the position of the minimum and the relative placement of the different $\log f_{\pm}$ vs. concentration curves being determined, for the same valence-type electrolytes, by the particular a value chosen (the larger the a value, the higher is the value of f_{\pm} , at the same concentration, and lower the concentration at which the re-increase of f_{\pm} begins). Assuming as correct the general result from solvation studies that the smaller the bare-cation radius the greater is the extent of its hydration and larger

19. (a) H. S. Harned and B. B. Owen, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolyte Solutions", Reinhold Pub. Co., New York, 3rd edition, 1958, Appendix A., p. 731.

(b) *ibid.*, p 725.

therefore the hydrated-cation radius, this is also roughly the general nature and order of placement of the actually observed $\log f_{\pm}$ vs. concentration curves of the different alkali and alkaline earth halides. Among different valence-type electrolytes again, the calculated f_{\pm} values for the higher valence types show a sharper variation with concentration (steeper initial decrease, followed by an earlier and steeper re-increase, after passing through a much lower placed minimum) as compared to those for the lower valence types (c.f. the curves for 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes with the same a_{\pm} value ($=2.66 \text{ \AA}$), in fig. 2). This again agrees with the actual experimental results for different valence type electrolytes.

2. The high potential solution of the Poisson equation is seen to lead to results which in certain cases may be considerably different from those from the low potential solution, both for the distribution formula 1 (particularly) as also 2 (for moderately large a valued 1-1 and 2-1 electrolytes at high concentrations, for example). Generally however, the two results do not differ greatly, upto moderate concentrations. The high potential solution leads in every case to larger f_{\pm} values as compared to those from the low potential solution (smaller the a value, the larger the difference, for same valence type electrolytes). This is equally true for both overlap-corrected and uncorrected curves.

3. The application of the overlap correction is seen to result in a general lowering of the $\log f_{\pm}$ vs. concentration curves, i.e. to smaller f_{\pm} values as compared to those obtained when this correction is neglected. This is true both for the results from the low-potential solution as also for those from the high-potential solution; their relative placement remaining unaffected by the use of the correction.

4. The results from the distribution formula (1) are seen (fig. 5) to be much less satisfactory from the point of view of experimental results, than those from the formula (2)*. No re-increase of activity coefficient values at higher concentrations can be seen, from either of the solutions of the Poisson equation; the lower placed (low-potential solution) $\log f_{\pm}$ vs. concentration curve being in fact the Debye-Hückel curve which is already known to be incapable of showing this effect. The application of the overlap correction to the high potential solution (c.f. the curve for $a=1.81 \text{ \AA}$ in fig. 3) is seen to result in a lowering of the f_{\pm} values, in much the same manner as in the case of the distribution formula (2), though the magnitude of the lowering is smaller here.

5. The use of the relation $b_{\pm}^0 = \frac{4\pi}{3} a_{\pm}^3$ is seen (fig. 4) to result in a general spreading-out of all $\log f_{\pm}$ vs. concentration curves as compared to those obtained by use of the relation: $b^0 = \frac{4\pi}{3} (2a_{\pm})^3$, i.e. in a more gradual variation of f_{\pm} with

* As a possible interpretation of this, an observation by Frank and Tsao²⁰ in reference to the Eigen-Wicke distribution (similar to our formula 2) may be cited here. The volume exclusion between ions of unlike sign, which in the Debye-Hückel model usually bear to each other the relation: central ion—cloud ion, is already taken into account in a way in the ion size parameter a . The alternative distribution function proposed may therefore plausibly neglect this, and restrict itself exclusively to considering volume exclusion between ions of like sign only. This would make formula (2) more likely to succeed empirically than formula (1).

concentration. By comparison with the actual experimental data for any particular electrolyte chosen, it would be seen that though somewhat larger a values have to be used in case of the relation $b_{\pm}^0 = \frac{4\pi}{3} a^3$, the course of the experimental points can then be somewhat better reproduced theoretically. Bearing in mind the already discussed interpretation of the quantity $b^0 \left(= \frac{4\pi}{3} (\text{diameter})^3 \right)$, this may be taken to indicate essentially that the ionic model 'charge at the centre of sphere' is more successful than the model 'charge uniformly spread over the surface'.

DISCUSSION

The theoretical justifiability of the Debye-Hückel method of calculation of ionic activity coefficients has been very thoroughly and critically analysed by a number of workers²¹ from the view-point of rigorous statistical mechanical theory. Hückel and Land Krafft²² have investigated this point in respect of the Eigen-Wicke theory, and have shown by using the analytical method developed by Kirkwood^{21c}, that the consideration of finite ionic dimensions cannot properly lead to a distribution function of the type considered by Eigen-Wicke; and that the statistical-mechanically justified distribution function which should be used instead cannot reproduce the postulated agreement between the theoretically calculated and experimentally observed course of f_{\pm} vs. concentration curves. Also, Frank and Tsao²⁰ have pointed out among a number of other important points of criticism, that the expression for activity coefficient obtained from the Eigen-Wicke theory by using the Güntelberg charging process^{19c} is different from that obtained by the Debye charging process, and is by contrast incapable of showing a rise of $\log f_{\pm}$ above zero at higher concentrations.

Now, the Eigen-Wicke and the Dutta - Bagchi distribution formulae having been shown³ to be essentially identical, the above points of criticism obviously apply equally well to the results obtained from the Dutta - Bagchi formula. The following may therefore be put forward in support of our method of calculation.

The phase integral of Gibbs is known to give a rigorous and adequate description of all systems of interacting particles, provided of course that both attractive and repulsive forces between the particles are properly taken into account. For describing the latter, the rigid sphere model of the particles (embodied in the ion-size parameter a) is usually a sufficiently good and simple approximation. On the other hand, the assumption that Coulombic interaction alone need be considered as sufficiently descriptive of all *attractive* forces in assemblies of charged particles may not be entirely

19 (c) *ibid.*, p. 60.

20. H. S. Frank and M. S. Tsao, *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 5, 43.

21. (a) R. H. Fowler, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1927, 23, 434; R. H. Fowler and E. A. Guggenheim, "Statistical Thermodynamics", Cambridge University Press, 1949, Ch. IX.

(b) L. Onsager, *Chem. Rev.*, 1933, 13, 73.

(c) J. G. Kirkwood, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, 2, 767.

22. E. Hückel and G. Krafft, *Z. phys. Chem.*, (Fr.), 1955, 3, 135; 1955, 5, 305.

E. Wicke and M. Eigen, *Z. phys. Chem.* (Fr.), 1955, 3, 178; 1955, 5, 312

justified; *short-range* inter-particle attractive forces may also be plausibly assumed to have an important role to play. The dominant thermodynamic characteristics of the system may well be determined by the dominant (long range) Coulomb attractive forces, but neglect of yet other attractive forces ('dispersion forces') present, might not be entirely justified^{21a}, and might essentially be responsible for some of the present unsatisfactory features of the Debye-Hückel type of treatments. Only true imperfect-gas type statistics, embodying adequately both (short-range) attractive and repulsive forces, should properly be considered as adequate possible replacements for the Boltzmann formula, in its application to ionic solution theory, say.

Such distribution formulae, in so far as it appears, will essentially be further extensions of formulæ of the type presently under consideration. Therefore investigations into the utility of the latter (limited) formulæ for purpose of use in electrolyte theory, do not appear to be basically incorrect, or even unnecessary, though they might well be looked upon as 'incomplete' in the sense mentioned.

In discussing their performance, it should be remembered first of all that the theoretical limit of validity of the Debye-Hückel type of treatments has been variously estimated, for 1-1 electrolytes of average-magnitude ionic radius for example, at between 10^{-3} to 10^{-1} m/lit. It has further been suggested that at higher concentrations, in addition to the intrinsic limitations of the Poisson-Boltzmann type combinations, the gradual preponderance of ion-solvent interactions^{24a,b}, short-range inter-ionic attractive forces, etc. begin to tell^{24c}. In view of this, it would indeed be an over-simplification to assume that the course of the activity coefficient curves over the entire concentration range could be reproduced theoretically on the basis of the Debye-Hückel or essentially equivalent models (as of the present paper) alone.* Ignoring on this count the rather satisfactory features of the present results in the region of high concentrations, it may yet be noted that even at low concentrations, the present results are not exactly identical with those from the Debye-Hückel theory (though they undoubtedly tend towards it), and there are small but significant deviations.

The high potential solution of the Poisson equation is seen to lead to results which, except in certain cases mentioned, are generally not significantly different

23. H. S. Frank and P. T. Thompson in "The Structure of Electrolyte Solutions", ed. W. J. Hamer, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1959, p. 113.

24. (a) R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stokes, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths Scientific Publications, 2nd Edition, London, 1959.

(b) E. Glueckauf in "The Structure of Electrolyte Solutions", ed. W. J. Hamer, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1959, p. 97.

(c) G. Scatchard, in "The Structure of Electrolyte Solutions", ed. W. J. Hamer, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1959, p. 9.

* Frank and Tsao²⁰ justify the neglect of ion-hydration correction on the line of Robinson and Stokes^{24a} in the present type model, by observing that the removal of water from its solvent function (which is what hydration correction essentially does) would be essentially equivalent to making certain regions of configuration space inaccessible for ion-distribution; which effect is already realistically taken into consideration in the new distribution functions. And that, moreover, such a treatment is logically preferable to the use of the Debye-Hückel distribution in which a takes care of only a portion of the inaccessibility, plus a supplementary (hydration) correction to take care of the rest.

(particularly for the formula 2) from those from the low potential solution. It would appear that the particular method of fit used above is responsible for this. The fit of the two potential solutions at $\lambda = m$ signifies essentially a fit at a concentration where the charge density round any ion (equation 4) approaches the limiting value physically possible (equation 3). This has the consequent added disadvantage that immediately beyond the transition concentration, the total available volume in the solution is taken up by the exclusion volumes of the different ions, because the neighbourhood of each is already maximally packed by ions of opposite sign. The continuation of activity coefficient calculations to higher concentration would properly require therefore the use of overlap corrections of rapidly increasing orders for the ionic exclusion volumes; the use of the second order correction is already seen to extend by a little the concentration range over which calculations are possible.* However, the transition to the high potential solution then also occurs at correspondingly higher concentration, so that the said difficulty in the proper study of its performance essentially remains.** The same is true in case the relation $b_{\pm}^0 = \frac{4\pi}{3} a_{\pm}^3$ is used.

However, this solution remains interesting nevertheless, particularly for systems where concentration—variation of the property studied is not of primary significance, e.g. in the case of electrokinetic and stability properties of colloidal suspensions^{1, 8}. The statistical mechanical difficulties which beset the use of the accurate solution of the Poisson-Boltzmann equation in electrolyte solution systems have further been shown^{2, 5} to be of much less significance here. Moreover the colloid particles being much more highly charged than simple ions, the possible usefulness in such systems of solutions of the Poisson equation worked out explicitly for the case when the potential is high, is obvious.

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* Analytical expressions for this, for different valence type electrolytes, can easily be deduced both when overlap correction is neglected, or taken into account.

** Certain alternative 'fits' have been investigated with a view to circumvent this difficulty, however none is as satisfactory, essentially because the fit at $\lambda = m$ is the most 'natural'.

25. H. B. G. Casimir in 'Tweede Symposium over sterke elektrolyten en over de elektrische dubbellaag', ed. Sectie voor Kolloidchemie der Ned. Chem. Ver. Utrecht, 1944 (cited in "Colloid Science" I, ed. H. R. Kruyt, Elsevier Pub. Co. Amsterdam, 1952, p. 129).